

THE ROLE AND SIGNIFICANCE OF MUSIC IN THE APPLICATION OF PEDAGOGICAL TECHNOLOGIES

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Annotation: This article provides full information on the skills to increase the pedagogical potential of music culture teachers, the methods of using pedagogical technologies in music lessons, and the use of various methods to increase students' interest in music lessons. .

Keywords: music, culture, method, teacher, skill, lesson, song, interest, pedagogical technologies, task, student.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada musiqa madaniyati o'qituvchilarining pedagogik salohiyatini oshirish bo'yicha ko'nikmalar, musiqa darslarida pedagogik texnologiyalardan foydalanish usullari va o'quvchilarni musiqa darslariga qiziqishini orttirish bo'yicha turli xil metodlardan foydalanish bo'yicha to'liq ma'lumot berilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: musiqa, madaniyat, metod, o'qituvchi, mahorat, dars, qo'shiq, qiziqish, pedagogik texnologiyalar, vazifa, o'quvchi.

Аннотация: В данной статье представлена полная информация о способах повышения педагогического потенциала учителей музыкальной культуры, методах использования педагогических технологий на уроках музыки, использовании различных методов повышения интереса учащихся к занятиям музыкой.

Ключевые слова: музыка, культура, метод, учитель, мастерство, урок, песня, интерес, педагогические технологии, задание, ученик.

Over the past period, the Republic of Uzbekistan has adopted a number of normative and legal acts on the development of culture and arts[1]. In particular, the Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PD - 3391 of November 17, 2017 " On measures to further develop the art of the Uzbek national makom", of May 30, 2019 " On the organization of the activities of the state museum-reserves Sarmishsay", "Shakhrisabz", "Termez" and "Kokand" Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 443 of April 21 [2] , 2020 "On measures to further increase the efficiency of the fine and applied arts" Resolution No. PD - 4688 of May 26, 2020 "Culture Decree No. PD-6000 of May 23 [3]. As we carry out music education and training in music culture classes, in front of the teacher, first of all, students should be interested in the art of music, the lessons they are taking, the knowledge being imparted, and the tunes and songs being studied. should be a wake-up call. Singing in

school, especially in elementary grades, plays an important role in the development and formation of the interest and inclination to listen to music, the positive attitude of young people to the art of music, and the development of their needs.

By its very nature, a music lesson is both an art and an educational lesson. Organizing it in a colorful and interesting way requires great pedagogical and professional skills from every teacher. In this place, it is of particular importance to ensure the creative activity of students during musical lessons. Understanding music, enjoying its emotional impact depends on the participation of emotional feelings as well as knowledge, skills and abilities.

The more active and deep the emotions are in the performance and perception of the work, the more conscious and effective their understanding and mastering, and being affected by them will be. These situations are a process that occurs as a result of creative activity. Student interest in the lesson depends primarily on the repertoire and methods (traditional or interactive methods) chosen for listening and performance. The main criterion of the repertoire of selected works depends on their age, interest, level of knowledge and skills.

Accordingly, the methods used should be more playful. The works related to the characters of fairy tales, animals, birds, plants, natural scenes, birds, which are organized in various competitions with the participation of dance, play, and thematic, are suitable for children's world. learns, develops aesthetic feelings, musical abilities. In these 27 places, along with modern songs, the use of folk songs, works of brotherly peoples and composers will make the lessons more meaningful and active, a strong influence on the formation of feelings of affection and love for the heritage of folk music in young people. It's a secret.

Creative activity occurs in every lesson. The composition and dramaturgy of the lesson, its artistic-pedagogical idea, goals and tasks, forms, methodical methods and technologies are also used to increase students' interest in music and educational materials, to instill in them the spiritual content of musical art and culture. , understanding of modern musical creative activity - all this is a product of the teacher's creative approach.

When the teacher plans a music lesson, he determines the purpose, task, topic, type and forms of teaching, musical activities and the knowledge, methods, and technologies to be imparted to the students in their content, and then creates the scenario of the lesson. Each activity of the lesson: listening to music, singing as a team, musical literacy, rhythmic movements, accompaniment on musical instruments, games - should be integrated by connecting with each other.

Various technologies, tools, methods and methods are used to actively involve students in the lesson. Any pedagogical technology should be based on educational principles that develop a new project of education and should be focused on the personality of the student. Cooperation between teacher and student, students and teacher should be organized on the basis of modern requirements, mutual communication, mutual influence.

In this process, the skills of working in cooperation with students are formed. In contrast to the methodical development of the educational process focused on the active, effective activity of students, the pedagogical technology of education focuses on learners, as well as their individual and joint activities with the teacher. creates conditions for mastering the material. There are many technologies used in the teaching process. These technologies will be designed for the age of the students, mass education or individual training.

Currently, the interest in applying new pedagogical technologies to the educational process is growing day by day. Because pedagogical technology and interactive methods make it easy and convenient for young students to acquire thorough knowledge and skills. Here we will briefly touch on some technologies that we have used in our practical experience. Dance + smile. These technologies can be used more in primary classes.

Use of dance tunes “Kari Navo”, “Dutor Bayoti”, “Andijan Polka”, “Dilkhijroj” from the textbooks of the first and fourth grade gives good results. In this, the students involved in the game-dance stand in any position they want. The teacher invites all the students to dance to pleasant music.

1. Students dance freely. When the music ends, he should say a word of applause to his friend who stopped by him with a smile.

2. It is strictly forbidden to criticize or discourage anyone. Students can be addressed as follows: “I was happy to see you dance”, “You dance beautifully”, “I really liked your dance techniques”, etc.

2. Pantomime style. Students sit in a circle. The teacher distributes pictures of musical instruments to students. The students’ task is to demonstrate with actions how to play the melody on these instruments. The rest must follow and find which musical instrument is shown. For example, if there is a picture of a circle in the picture, he shows with hand movements while sitting on a chair, Trumpet, Trumpet, Gjizhak, Rubob, Dutor, Piano, musical instruments with appropriate hand movements is described. It will be discussed after the performance of 5-6 students.[4]

3. Please continue. (for revision lessons) The class is divided into two groups. Group 1 starts one of the songs taught in previous lessons, the first couplet is sung, group 2 continues. The group that continues correctly will be the winner and will have the right to choose the 2nd song. After 3 songs, the absolute winner will be determined and evaluated. 4. "Bilaghon Street" style. In this technology, students are divided into groups (4-5), each group is shown portraits of composers.

Pupils tell the names of composers' lives, activities, works, and sing some excerpts from their works.

Libra style. This method summarizes past topics with more evidence and compares them with the answers of other group participants. The group with the clear, correct answer is the winner.

The use of pedagogical technologies aimed at making students think, observe, demonstrate their knowledge, ingenuity, and ingenuity, while democratizing the lesson process, develops cooperation between the teacher and students, and students' creativity. Constant working communication and relationship between the teacher and the students is important for increasing the effectiveness of the lesson and expanding the scope of knowledge of the students.

Interactive methods are a factor of creating a creative environment in the lesson based on the mutual cooperation of the teacher and students, increasing the effectiveness of the lesson, forming the skills of students to think independently, to express their attitude. In such methods, the student, with his active participation, tries to find answers to problems and questions individually, in pairs, in groups, as a team, thinks, evaluates, writes, speaks, gives evidence and reasons for the problem. tries to explain.

This will remain firmly in the memory of students. Teaches a critical, analytical approach to mastering a new topic (information). There are many types of interactive methods. We will dwell on some of them that we have used in our work:

"Brainstorming" method. "Brainstorming" is a learning method that allows each student in the class to express their opinion on a question or problem posed by the teacher. The essence of the method is to gather together all the options of possible opinions on the problem or question set by the teacher, and to take into account all the opinions of students, including those that are not quite correct.

In order to participate well in this, you need to write down all these ideas on the board or special writing paper. This allows students to correctly understand the

question or problem in the further analysis of the stated ideas. Methods of "Brainstorming".

1. The teacher asks the class a question, task or problem and invites the students to express their opinions.

2. As an exception, all ideas (the more the better) are written on the board or flipchart.

3. After all the ideas are written down, the teacher forms all the ideas with the students, corrections are made to the said ideas. Later, the most important ones will be highlighted in order to use it. Rules for "Brainstorming".

1. Observance of the time regulation for conducting "Aqly attack";

2. To give an opportunity to all those who wish to express their opinion within the specified time;

3. Opinions expressed by students should not be criticized, discussed or evaluated;

4. If necessary, corrections should be made to the stated opinion. But it should be for the purpose of expressing an idea or an idea clearly and briefly;[5]

Cluster method: When using this method, "Uzbek folk instruments" is the "key" word and is written on the board. Information about Uzbek folk musical instruments is presented and organized by groups using the cluster method. At the end of the lesson, homework will be given on the subject.

This method improves students' ability to justify their own point of view, penetrate into the ideas of others, and work in a group. Technological map of the lesson "Instrumental ensemble" according to the curriculum of the third quarter of the 2nd grade. The topic of the quarter: "Types of ensembles, what is a tune?" What does the tune represent?

The purpose of the lesson: to teach students to think independently and creatively; to give an understanding of musical ensembles; strengthening students' skills of listening to music and singing as a team.

Lesson method: mixed Lesson equipment: 2nd grade music textbook;

Piano and musical instruments;

Visual and illustrative exhibitions on music literacy;

Sheet music poster of the song; Technical tools.

Course of the lesson: Students enter the classroom to the sound of music. Organizational part: attendance is monitored with the help of an attendant, the topic is announced. New topic: a conversation about the spring season will be held regarding the song "Spring Song" : that is planned to be learned in the group singing activity.

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“Chigil wrote” method. If this method (technology) is used in the last parts of the lesson, it will enliven and raise the mood of students who have been sitting in one place for 40-45 minutes. Students of the class organize a competition in rows. - Pupils from each line should dance to the tune.

The repertoire of tunes should be composed in such a way that they should be different in terms of tempo, and if possible, music of different nationalities. In this way, the ingenuity of students will be able to independently accept music with inner feelings, and besides, they will be able to get acquainted with the music of other nations. The main thing is that this method increases the psychological stability of students, improves their mood, and increases their attention to music lessons.

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